

PWR COMPOSITE MATERIALS USE: A PARTICULAR CASE OF SAFETY-RELATED SERVICE WATER PIPES

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this document is to present the broadening use of composites in French nuclear and fossil-fuel power plants. Some possible applications are presented ; the case of epoxy glass piping has been the subject of precise studies and of modeling. The general conclusions obtained are that the selected manufacturing method and materials (filament wound epoxy glass) meet the specifications of EDF. In certain areas, there is a need to go deeper into the understanding of the phenomenon, for aging particularly, because the pipeworks are expected to last the lifetime of the plant. The design rules used are convenient, but the margins need to be specified. NDT methods are available.

KEYWORDS: composite piping, power plants, selection of materials, aging, design rules, NDT, safety-related applications

INTRODUCTION

In PWR nuclear plants, steel water piping (particularly service water piping and fire pipeworks) undergo rapid corrosion. EDF has decided to install composite material piping in the latest built nuclear plant in Civaux for most of the water circuits apart from the reactor building. Some of those circuits are classified « nuclear safety », their integrity must be safeguarded. This important choice underlines the interest that EDF takes in the development of these new materials, but demands great R&D efforts (for example design studies, qualification of suppliers and quality control procedures, manufacturing and aging processes, non destructive examination either during installation or in service). These efforts ties up EDF's position with the aeronautic and aerospace industries.

Where the aeronautic and aerospace industries seek to associate functional safety and design optimization (performance/weight ratio) generally at a high price, EDF tends to seek functional safety and long term durability (40 years) at a competitive price.

Certain industries such as aeronautic, armament, and chemical take a several years lead on EDF in many fields ; alignment with them would be of great benefit for many of the research subjects mentioned above.

TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR EDF

General Applications for EDF

Many applications are obviously possible, among which EDF gives priority to the following fields:

- piping (enlargement on Class 3 safety-related and non-classified circuits),
- structural composites (framework, roofing truss,....),
- tanks,
- fixtures and fittings within buildings (access ramps, ladders, floor grating, hand rails, guard rails like in the Petit Saut dam in Guyana);

Other applications could be considered : valves, pipe support work, raceways, cable trays, armor cladding and anti-projectile protection, fan blades for cooling towers, fuel storage pools, release flues, cable chase and ventilation shafts, tooling and equipment for live work (scaffolding, platforms,...), conductors with a composite central core, fire doors, panel boards, etc.

The materials under study are glass fiber reinforced thermoset resins (epoxy, vinyl ester and polyester). For piping applications, the filament winding technique is the most suitable. On the other hand, composite joinery (gratings, ladders, handrails, etc.) requires pultrusion techniques.

In order to develop composites for EDF's applications and to acquire the competence required to verify manufacturers' designs, R & D is necessary on three major outlines:

- knowledge of the aging process to reach a prediction of life time (resistance to hydrolysis, to creep, to acid/base/salt corrosion, to stress etc.) ;
- knowledge of the specific design rules (for multi-layer, heterogeneous, anisotropic materials) and development of the required and optimized rules and codes;
- knowledge of the different non-destructive testing methods for:
 - inspection during manufacture,
 - final inspection,
 - in service inspection.

Quality Assurance and the Materials

The nature of the materials implies the introduction of a strong quality assurance policy. The quality of supplies depends on the one of the raw materials, but above all on the manufacturing process and on the assembly of the structure on site. A procedure for the qualification of the suppliers and their operators, for the monitoring of manufacture and assembly on site, for the analysis of the feedback is necessary.

A Review of the General Use of Composite Piping

Since 1960, power stations, paper mills, chemical plants, the petrochemical industry and local councils have significantly increased their use of composite material piping throughout the world (particularly in the United States) for the following applications :

- desulfurization plants (cooling tower, piping...),
- networks for cooling water,
- networks for acids and other corrosive products,

ducts for effluent, waste water, wash water etc.,
piping for outflow, irrigation networks,
ducts for the desalination of salt water.

French Power Stations

Hydroelectric power stations do not use composite piping.

Fossil fuel power plants use this type of piping, in cooling or chlorinating circuits, in purge of wash water, and in flue gas desulfurization.

Nuclear power stations, however, are more fully equipped with composite piping (several tens of kilometers of composite piping) without any significant problem in terms of assembly or operation.

All the piping in the operating nuclear park is non-safety-related.

In the future, there will probably be a major increase in the use of composite piping, in particular within the scope of back-fitting programs for the fire-protection circuits and the safety-related service water circuits, once our selections have been justified before and approved by the French Safety Authorities.

Abroad

Hydroelectric power stations abroad do not use composite piping with the exception of the particular cases of inaccessible areas which can only be reached by helicopter and where light weight is the criterion of choice.

Fossil fuel power stations are major consumers of composite piping for the water circuits, but above all for the flue gas desulfurization system (Europe, Japan, USA). Data are available about certain American installations on the use of composite piping over a period of nearly 25 years with no apparent deterioration.

These comments are also valid for nuclear power plants. A vast inquiry, carried out at an international level (Western Europe, Japan, USA), in direct contact with the utilities, and in collaboration with the manufacturers and using data bases, reveals that the use of composite tubing in non safety-related applications is significant, but on the other hand, that in safety-related applications it is almost at zero level. Only three examples of the use of composites in safety-related piping are known to date (Belgium, USA).

The Technical Solutions

Two large families of composite structures can be used for piping:

Dual Laminate (Thermoplastic Reinforced with GRP)

This technique consists in rolling layers of resin-impregnated reinforcement (fibers or woven rovings) onto a thermoplastic liner. The liner is first heat-sealed, GRP is then built up on the outside to constitute the stress-resistant layer which bears the load.

The disadvantages in comparison to GRP (see below) are:
burdensome solution (manufacture and assembly),
limited resistance to temperature.

The advantages are:
perfect continuity of the inner-liner by heat-sealing,
excellent chemical resistance.

This latter advantage makes it a very appreciated technical solution in the chemical industry for the transfer or storage of extremely corrosive products (acid, alkali...).

GRP

In this solution, the anti-corrosion layer is a thermosetting resin lightly reinforced by a fine glass fiber fabric. The load-bearing layer, much richer in fibers, has the same chemical nature as the anti-corrosion layer. It is the best technico-economic compromise for our requirements (service water for example).

The main disadvantages of the composite material option are :

- little feedback at EDF,
- need to acquire a good knowledge of the material,
- structures sensitive to shocks,
- low level of world-wide standardization,
- few developed NDT methods.

There are however numerous advantages:

- excellent corrosion resistance (absence of significant corrosion over several decades),
- lightness,
- commercial availability in all qualities and diameters (25 mm to 9000 mm, even 11000 mm),
- minimal maintenance (no painting required),
- low pressure drop (thanks to very low roughness),
- quick and easy repair,
- very good resistance to fire (when filled with water).

For the applications in the nuclear power plants of EDF, the choice of basic material is relatively simple : GRP using a thermosetting resin. Epoxy has been chosen for the piping at CIVAU, as it provides the best compromise between stress and chemical resistance when used for long term service water applications.

Manufacturing Method

The manufacturing methods suitable for the achievement of cylindrical sections are few:

- contact molding,
- pultrusion,
- low pressure injection,
- centrifuging,
- filament winding.

Of all these techniques, filament winding is undoubtedly the most suitable. It is possible to control the winding angle (from 0 to 90° with respect to the rotational axis).

The advantages are the following :

- fibers laid under controlled tension, in the desired direction (optimization possible),
- high fiber content,
- possibility of automation (guaranteed reproducibility).

On-site Assembly

The ways to join piping elements are butt and wrap joints, or adhesive joints (either cylindrical/conical or conical/conical), threaded sleeves, or bolted flange-to-flange connection or rotating flange (composite flange without pre-drilling).

To summarize, the safety-related composite piping at CIVAUX are made of glass fiber and epoxy resin (GRP). Straight pipes are filament wound and fittings use wound woven rovings. The adhesive joints are either cylindrical/conical or conical/conical. Joints with metal parts (pumps, valves, exchangers, etc.) use flanges.

The Economic Aspect

The decision to use piping in composite materials should be based on a full technico-economic analysis (investment, maintenance, savings in pumping energy, savings in assembly time....) of the different solutions available.

An objective comparison must therefore be made taking into account the overall costs (supply, fitting and maintenance) over the full service life of the plant. The comparison has to be made between Steel and Composite Material. The prices put forward for the design, supply, manufacture and assembly generally follow some general principles:

-for a diameter ≥ 400 mm:

The prices for GRP piping on a straight run (gallery for example) are comparable to those of coated or stainless steel. In the case of circuits including a great number of fittings or special parts (pumping station for example), the price of GRP piping is higher, due to the cost of elbows, reductions, T-joints and take-off points.

-for a diameter ≤ 250 mm:

The composite material solution is the most economical, despite the singularities (standardization of fittings in commonly available diameters).

The increased cost sometimes brought about by the use of composite materials is largely compensated by their technical advantage in terms of corrosion resistance.

THE STUDY OF SAFETY-RELATED GRP WATER PIPING

Research & Development Program

EDF has at the moment an Ongoing Research & Development Project (ORDP or PPRD in French) "Composite Materials Circuits". Priority is voluntarily given to the circuits for the nuclear power plant of CIVAUX. The efforts in terms of R & D and design studies are therefore concentrated, in the short term, on epoxy-glass piping for safety-related and non-safety-related circuits. This exercise must be a total success if a widespread development of this type of composite structure within EDF is expected in the years to come.

The objectives of the R & D program are, on the one hand, to evaluate industrial practice regarding manufacture, quality control, design rules and in-service inspection procedures and, on the other hand, to develop and validate models forecasting long term aging and mechanical behavior.

The program hinges upon the following five main axes.

1st Axis: Selection of Basic Material and Manufacturing Process,

The objective is to establish a set of guidelines to facilitate the evaluation of selection criteria for materials and existing industrial manufacturing processes.

2nd Axis: Quality Control During Manufacture,

The implementation of the quality control procedures (methods, tools, criteria) for different types of products (thin or thick structures) taking into account the basic material used (resin ductility, winding type, etc.) and the specific service conditions requires the establishment of a set of guidelines. The manufacturing defects and defects in adhesive joints have to be evaluated and the specification of the associated inspection criteria and methods to be written.

3rd Axis: Long Term Mechanical Behavior,

Through the development and validation of models of long term mechanical behavior taking into account the effects of humid environment, the long term objective is to finalize a predictive method to reach the service life of products under pressure in the presence of water.

4th Axis: Design Rules

EDF has selected standards or codes for safety-related circuits (code CASE N155-2 by ASME). They have to be evaluated, and more precisely, the margins that they allow must be clarified on the basis of the results obtained from experiments and computer modeling.

5th Axis: Non-Destructive Testing In Service.

There is a need for a set of guidelines about the methods of in-service inspection: description of the methods, implementation, performances, criteria.

Main Results

1st Axis: Selection of Basic Material and Manufacturing Process

Up to now, EDF has acquired the necessary knowledge of the industrial environment. The manufacturing processes are also well evaluated : they have been described above in accordance to the types of use they could meet. Filament winding of either roving or stripes has proven to have a better behavior than centrifugation.

A choice has been made of a set of resins that could be used in the selected possible applications in EDF power plants : the resins could be either isophthalic polyester, or vinylester, or epoxy. If the studies are restricted to a further use for water piping with safety-related applications, isophthalic polyester is not considered (it might be taken into account for joinery for example, or for non safety-related piping). A general study of the hydrolytic resistance of the macromolecular skeleton has led to a classification of the resins according to the different chemical links they bear. The links are classified in increasing order of fragility versus hydrolysis : nitrile < ester < ether.

Water uptake is a reversible phenomenon in the first place, which leads to a plastification of the macromolecular network underlined by a decrease in Young's modulus (0 to 20% for the studied resins) and of the glass transition temperature. Then, an hydrolysis occurs, and it is an irreversible phenomenon.

Epoxy resins can be synthesized with different hardeners. Epoxy-anhydride are disappointing as soon as the service temperature rises above 60°C ; for higher temperatures, EDF will prefer epoxy-amine type resins. As far as mechanics and hydrolysis are concerned, epoxy-amine and vinylester meet our requirements.

2nd Axis: Quality Control During Manufacture

The points to evaluate were the harmfulness of the manufacturing defects, the shock resistance and the non destructive control methods that could be used at this stage. Defects in straight pipes such as the core delaminations, or a delamination between the liner and the mechanical layer, an interruption in the roving, or pores in the liner don't affect the leaking pressure. A bad impregnation of the roving by the resin at least on 3 layers, is harmful for the leaking pressure. Adhesive joints present a high tolerance to adhesive defects. The following criterion have been published by the Dutch society KEMA for the harmfulness of those defects:

« The surface of the defect should be less than 25% of the total surface of the joint.

The residual length of adhesive along a generating line should be higher than 20% of the total length.

The total length of an adhesive defect leading to the inner part of the pipe should be less than 30% of the total length of the joint.

The glass transition temperature of the adhesive should be higher than the level [Optimum glass temperature of the adhesive - 30°C] ».

On the basis of those criterion, a long term program will shortly begin in order to follow the evolution versus time of instantaneously acceptable defects in adhesive joints. The bending behavior of piping is a great concern as well, for the answer to seisms. It is being studied by EDF. The MARINETECH program in Great Britain is cosponsored by EDF ; among other research themes interesting the understanding of composites, a work package deals with mechanical properties : fatigue, creep, etc. under different loading modes.

The shock resistance has been evaluated for a shock between 0 and 120 Joules. The minimum impact energy that leads to a leak has been determined for representative diameters. Until 90 Joules roughly, the leak rate stays very weak (less than 0.15 l/h for a 150 mm diameter). If plotted versus time, the leak rate of damaged pipes maintained under service pressure without end closure is annealed after a few weeks, which is favorable. This behavior had already been reported by oil producing firms, but those tests are still underway : the residual leak pressure has to be measured and the problem of testing pipes with or without end closure to be thought about.

A new non destructive method for the evaluation of the polymerization state of the resin by use of a piezoelectric implant has been designed. It is now under further study to see whether it could give an account of the aging of the structure.

3rd Axis: Long Term Mechanical Behavior

The aim, in this part of the project, was to evaluate the mechanisms and the kinetics of the damages that can occur in composite piping. A predictive model for the long term behavior and an accelerated aging method were requested. As the material is heterogeneous, and the degradation modes are complex, the adjustment of such a model is long and difficult. An additional difficulty is brought by the duration of the tests : to study the long term behavior (40 years), very long tests must be performed. Accelerated test procedures are being used to evaluate the loss of stiffness with time (for an extrapolation to 40 years). But the correlation between natural and accelerated aging is difficult and should be steadied.

The ASTM 2992 (American standard) which is called out by the Case N-155-2 code, is used to determine the long term mechanical strength of all the elements of the composite circuits in Civaux. This method has a satisfactory feedback among the oil field for example. To adjust all the parameters, a program of dismountable collars on the circuits in Civaux has been designed. It will help following the behavior of the material in service and compare the extrapolation resulting from the application of ASTM 2992 to natural aging. The results obtained and expected in those fields will be very helpful to give inputs for the model that has partially been written (for the mechanical part, not for the influence of hydrolysis for instance) and must be validated.

4th Axis: Design Rules

The critical reading of ASME's « CASE N-155-2 » code, used by EDF to design the safety-related circuits in Civaux has brought to the fore that complementary verifications are necessary to bring improvements in this design. The ruin mechanism of a composite structure depend on the type of stress and of material ; many tests have been performed at EDF on the structures used in Civaux. For the pipes and for nearly all the stresses, (pressure with end closure, pressure with end closure + bending, pressure with end closure + tension) under water pressure, a weeping is observed before the final ruin. The only exception is the test of pressure without end closure which leads directly to a wall fracture but at very high stress levels. Fittings, manufactured by stripe winding, do not weep. Their high mechanical strength leads to the fact that the weak part of the circuit around a fitting is the adhesive joint. The study of the adhesive joints proves thus to be a crucial point.

With ASTM 2992, it is possible to reach the long term mechanical strength of a pipe from weeping tests under pressure with end closure. But the circuits actually bear in service a stress with end closure and bending, so the validity of the method can be questioned. It has been proved that the short term weeping stress with end closure of a pipe is similar to this of a pipe under stress with end closure + bending.

In the calculations of the circuit's design, a flexibility factor k is introduced for the fittings ; it modelizes the flexibility of the fitting towards the straight pipe. The CASE code gives a pessimistic value for k : $k=1$, no flexibility of the fitting towards the straight pipe. An analytical formula for this coefficient has been defined and validated on the basis of tests and finite elements calculations.

5th Axis: Non-Destructive Testing In Service.

At the beginning of the R&D program, very few NDT methods (reliable, sensible and economical) for composite circuits were available. An evaluation of the 5 following techniques has been made :

IR Thermography,
differential interferometry (shearography),
ultrasonics,
acoustic emission,
X rays.

None of those techniques give all the answers. However, appropriate results have been obtained with X rays for adhesive joints bearing lack of adhesive, with ultrasonics for local controls, and with acoustic emission for the global control of pipeworks. Large scale X ray controls have been performed on joints of the Civaux power plant. These controls have put forward lacks of adhesive, sometimes of a large size. The procedures that were used for the installation (derived from the current industrial practical knowledge) have been improved and the quality of the joints is now greatly enhanced. The subsequent work (underway) is to justify the sorting criterion used, (according to the studies of the KEMA Society and together with the work by the MARINETECH Research Group) and to evaluate the harmfulness of the remaining defects.

The use of those NDT methods doesn't free from visual inspection, which is enough sensitive for most major damages (shocks for example) and gives a good general estimation of the quality of the circuits. A constant improvement of the implementation procedures would also lead to the possibility of limiting the use of expensive NDT methods through an increase in the confidence on the manufacturing and laying processes.

CONCLUSION

The installation of composite pipes in a nuclear plant in France is under way. The manufacturing methods and the products chosen are in good agreement with the specifications written by EDF. There is a need for a broadening of the knowledge about the adhesive and the fiber-matrix interface, and their behavior through aging. The leaking pressure is very tolerant to the defects in the pipes or in the joints. But the criterion followed up to now have to be validated with a higher precision. The realization of a predictive model to reach the lifetime of the materials is underway ; this action must be continued, and an accelerated aging procedure must be defined. The appropriate margin of the design rules must be reached, and specific rules for non-safety related circuits have to be proposed. Three NDT methods (acoustic emission, ultrasonics and X rays) are promising.

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